

Action of Light on Silver Bromide.

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It is well known that in the photochemical darkening of silver chloride, small quantities of oxygen are absorbed by the darkened product (see Macmahon, *J. Proc. Asiatic Soc. Bengal*, 1915, 11, 179). It is unnecessary to quote here the voluminous literature on the subject or to discuss the various theories which have been put forward to account for the nature and composition of the reduction product. Suffice to say that the theory of the formation of a sub-chloride Ag_2Cl , has now been generally discarded; that the existence of an oxychloride, Ag_2OCl , is extremely unlikely; and that the most probable assumption is the formation of a solid solution of dispersed silver particles in the unchanged silver chloride together with varying quantities of free metallic silver depending in amount upon the time and intensity of the exposure to light. The latter theory was put forward in the paper mentioned above by one of us (P. S. M.).

It is now of interest to see whether similar results are obtained by exposure of silver bromide to strong sunlight. For this purpose pure dry silver bromide was sealed up in a special vessel containing pure dry oxygen in a thermostat and the temperature and pressure noted. It was then exposed to sunlight for lengthy periods and any alteration in the volume of oxygen was measured. The bromine given off was absorbed by pure precipitated gold, thus avoiding the danger of the absorbent (Baker, for example used copper for this purpose) being accountable for any absorption of oxygen absorbed.

In all cases absorption of oxygen was clearly apparent and the reduced product was found to contain oxygen.

Silver bromide (prepared from chemically pure silver, dissolved in pure dilute nitric acid, precipitated with pure potassium bromide, washed thoroughly and dried over phosphorus pentoxide for several days in a dark room) was placed in a vessel which was sealed to a bulb containing pure precipitated gold. The bulb was joined to another vessel of the shape of a manometer through a three-way tube, one end of which was drawn to a point and left open for filling the

apparatus with oxygen after exhausting the air already present in it. The other two ends of the tube were joined to the bulb with gold and the manometric vessel respectively. The side of the manometric vessel nearer to the bulb was of a wider diameter than the other limb so as to allow more oxygen to remain in the apparatus when finally sealed. The narrow end of the manometric vessel was drawn to a point and sealed.

The whole apparatus, which was of a size convenient for immersion in a thermostat, was exhausted and filled with pure dry oxygen, allowed to remain in the thermostat for an hour, and then the open end of the three-way tube was sealed off under atmospheric pressure.

On exposure to sunlight, in the course of lengthy periods, by repeated shaking and exposure of fresh surfaces to the sun, an appreciable amount of decomposition was obtained. As in the case of silver chloride, this only amounted to a small portion of the mass of silver chloride in the vessel, inasmuch as the darkened outer layers form a thin protective covering over the bulk of each granule.

The apparatus was again put in the thermostat when sufficient decomposition had taken place, and the sealed end of the manometric vessel was cut open with the entire apparatus under water so that it could be sucked in case an absorption of oxygen had taken place.

The following give the results of typical experiments:—

TABLE I.

In this experiment the absorbent used was not a precipitate of pure gold but gold leaves.

Date when sealed	...	...	...	23. 12. 1924.
Date when opened	...	...	...	6. 1. 1926.
Weight of AgBr exposed	...	...	...	69.2 g.
Volume of O ₂ absorbed, reduced to N. T. P.	...	...	...	2.087 c.c.

The above absorption was observed with pure dry oxygen in the tube. The bulb was again sealed with the above exposed AgBr, but instead of dry oxygen, this time was filled with moist oxygen. Absorption of a fresh quantity of oxygen took place.

TABLE II.

Date when sealed	...	...	...	20. 1. 1926.
Date when opened	...	...	...	18. 2. 1926.
Volume of O ₂ further absorbed, reduced to N. T. P.	...	...	...	0.626 c.c.

Instead of using gold leaves as an absorbent for bromine, in the following experiment pure precipitate of gold was used with a fresh quantity of silver bromide.

TABLE III.

Date when sealed	...	...	...	...	8. 4. 1926.
Date when opened	...	...	...	...	20. 1. 1927.
Weight of AgBr exposed	...	...	...	...	49.9 g.
Volume of O ₂ absorbed, reduced to N. T. P.	...	...	...	...	1.064 c.c.

From the above experiments it has been definitely proved that silver bromide absorbs oxygen in approximately the same amount as that observed in the case of silver chloride. Moreover, the amount of absorption bears no quantitative relation to the mass of silver halide but depends on the extent of surface exposed. The oxygen absorbed was present in the darkened product as could be easily indicated by the production of an alkaline reaction when the reduced product was treated with pure neutral potassium chloride in a platinum or silica vessel. The photochemical darkening of silver bromide was also accelerated by the presence of oxidising agents; pure silver bromide was exposed to diffused day-light in two portions, one under boiled conductivity water, and the other under hydrogen peroxide (10 vol.). The latter changed colour rapidly, while the former only very slowly.

The question remains how to account for the small quantity of oxygen which is always present in the photo-halide. Baker has suggested the formation of an oxychloride in the case of silver chloride. It has been pointed out in the previous paper by one of us (*loc. cit.*) that all the reactions observed by Baker can be explained on the assumption that silver oxide (Ag_2O) is present. Moreover, the similarity in the behaviour of silver chloride and silver bromide in sunlight as regards absorption of small quantities of oxygen by the darkened surface layers can only point to one conclusion, namely, that it must be ascribed directly to the silver itself produced in the photochemical decomposition of the halide. In other words dispersed silver in solid solution in the photo-halide is capable of taking up oxygen under the conditions created in the above experiments. This behaviour is analogous to that of colloidal silver which even when prepared by Bredig's method from pure metallic silver, is found to contain oxide necessary

for its stable existence. It has been recently proved (Chapman, Ramsbottom and Trotman, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1925, A, 107, 100) that when silver is heated in oxygen at a pressure exceeding 0.005 mm. of mercury, it becomes almost completely covered with a film of oxide. Therefore, there is nothing improbable in the assumption that an exothermic reaction of the above type should take place spontaneously under the influence of light, especially when the metal is in such a fine state of subdivision.

Our next step was to endeavour to prepare disperse silver in weighable quantities and to find out if it can be directly oxidised by exposure to oxygen. A method for preparing this material was published by Fürth (*Kolloid Z.*, 1924, 34, 222), who obtained a deposit from an electric arc struck in air between two silver electrodes, and this powder gave a sol when dissolved in water. We have obtained disperse silver by Fürth's method and have observed that this deposit is by no means pure silver: it contains large quantities of the oxide and the nitrate. On igniting the deposit, brown fumes are given out in perceptible quantities.

The dust has been prepared by us by striking the arc between chemically pure silver electrodes in either air, oxygen or nitrogen. Nitrate was found to be produced in oxygen containing as little as 0.2 per cent. nitrogen. The same result was obtained in nitrogen containing traces of oxygen.

The properties of the solid powder were also investigated. There was evidence that this powder took up a further small quantity of oxygen indicating at least a partial oxidation of finally disperse silver.

The silver rods for the arc were made from pure silver prepared by the reduction of silver chloride with glucose.

A little of the silver dust prepared in air was taken in a crucible and heated gently so as to change the original grey colour into silvery white, and the loss in weight determined.

TABLE IV.

Weight of the freshly prepared dust taken for heating	...	0.2947 g.
Weight of pure silver left after heating		0.2923 g.
Weight of nitrogen and oxygen driven off		0.0023 g.
Amount of nitrogen and oxygen		0.78 per cent.

A little of the same original silver dust was taken and exposed in a desiccator in an atmosphere of dry oxygen free from carbon dioxide in sunlight to find if it absorbed a further quantity of oxygen during exposure.

TABLE V.

Weight of the original Ag dust taken for further exposure	...	...	0.2226 g.
Weight of the dust after a week's exposure	...	...	0.2285 g.
Weight of the pure silver left after heating	...	...	0.2309 g.
Percentage of O ₂ and N ₂ to pure silver left	...	...	1.18 percent.

From the above table it is seen that there is absorption of a further small quantity of oxygen during exposure.

Another sample of the disperse silver was again prepared by striking the arc in air and was divided into two equal parts, one was directly exposed to dry oxygen in sunlight and was then analysed: the other sample was weighed first and then exposed to dry oxygen in sunlight. The results obtained showed again that there was an increase in weight during exposure. Both these samples contained 0.8489 g. of nitrogen and oxygen for every 100 g. of pure silver produced on heating. In both the cases, the total quantity of nitrogen and oxygen after final exposure was found to be the same.

TABLE VI.

Weight of exposed dust taken	...	...	0.1316 g.
Weight of pure silver left on heating		...	0.1296 g.
Weight of nitrogen and oxygen	...	...	0.0020 g.

TABLE VII.

Weight of dust taken for exposure	...	...	0.1307 g.
Increase of weight due to the exposure	...	...	0.0009 g.
Weight of pure silver left after heating	...	...	0.1296 g.
Weight of N ₂ and O ₂ before exposure	...	...	0.0011 g.
Weight of N ₂ and O ₂ after exposure	..	...	0.0020 g.

From the above tables it is clear that finely divided silver is capable of further oxidation. It is of interest to note that the amount of volatile matter in the different samples of silver dust prepared by striking the arc in air, differs by a small quantity. In one case it was 0.7863 g. and in the other, it increased to 0.8459 g. per 100 g. of silver produced on heating the dust. It is evident that the amount of nitrogen and oxygen in the dust will necessarily depend on the size of the particles, and it is just possible that the size of the silver grains is not uniform even when the experiments are repeated under apparently identical conditions.

At present there seems to be enough experimental evidence in support of the view advanced in a former paper (*loc. cit.*) by one of us that molecular or colloidal silver is capable of being spontaneously oxidised in air. This being firmly established we venture to suggest that the formation of a photo-halide is due partly at least to the direct absorption of oxygen by the disperse silver produced in photochemical decomposition of the silver halide and is not due to the photochemical synthesis of an oxy-compound.

Summary

1. Pure dry silver bromide was sealed in a tube with oxygen using gold as an absorbent, and was then exposed to the tropical sun for lengthy periods. Absorption of oxygen occurred in all cases almost to the same extent as in the case of silver chloride.

2. The amount of absorption bears no quantitative relation to the mass of the silver halide exposed, but depends on the extent of surface exposed.

3. Oxygen is present in the darkened product.

4. The photochemical darkening of silver bromide is accelerated by the presence of oxidising agents.

5. Disperse silver was produced by striking an arc between two pure silver electrodes in air, oxygen and nitrogen. It has been found that the dust so prepared is by no means pure silver but is contaminated with oxide and nitrate in varying quantities.

6. Disperse silver produced in air is capable of further oxidation though to a small extent when exposed to dry oxygen.

7. The photo-halides formed are not due to the photochemical synthesis of an oxy-compound but are due partly at least to the direct absorption of oxygen by the disperse silver produced in the photochemical decomposition of silver halide so as to produce a partial oxidation of the disperse silver formed.

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P. S.—Our attention has been drawn to a recent paper (Chapman and Hall, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1929, 124, 478) in which the authors confirm the conclusion arrived at in this paper as regards the spontaneous oxidation of silver. They found that at the same temperature and pressure hydrogen molecules removed less heat from a hot metallic silver surface than from a surface of the same metal which has been subjected to the action of oxygen, indicating the formation of a surface layer of oxide.

They have also found from observations on the catalytic activity of silver wire that even at ordinary temperature a silver surface exposed to oxygen is immediately covered with a film of oxide.

